

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO MULTIPLE LOADS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a general purpose composite laminate optimization program based on linear and non-linear mathematical programming methods. The design of composite laminates for minimum weight, optimal thickness and maximum strength can efficiently be treated by this program whose architecture and capabilities are shortly described. As illustrative examples, bidirectional and multidirectional long-fiber laminates as well as composites with randomly oriented short-fibers, formed of different materials and subjected to multiple load conditions, are considered. The optimum thickness, minimum number of plies, optimum orientation and maximum strength of the laminate under consideration are determined, knowing the external applied forces and / or moments and taking into account the hygrothermal effects.

Keywords: design, optimization, composite laminates, microcomputer, software.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is generally recognized that composite materials are strong, durable and damage tolerant. They meet design and certification requirements and offer significant weight advantages. Design optimization of composite structures has gained importance in recent years as engineering applications of fiber-reinforced materials have increased and weight saving has become an essential design objective, especially for aircraft and spacecraft structures [1].

In fact, the design of composite materials involves "tailoring" the material itself, i.e. choosing the number of layers, their orientation, the stacking sequence and so on, in order to obtain the desired engineering characteristics. Consequently the optimization of composite laminates consists of finding these "optimum" tailoring parameters for a given loading condition. Many algorithms are available for the solution of the iterative search task. The optimization algorithms offered in this work are based on: Sequential Unconstrained Minimization Techniques, Method of Feasible Direction and Sequential Linear Programming [2,3].

The optimal design of composite materials and composite structures has been addressed by numerous investigators. Papers which have contributed to this area are presented by Shin et al [1], Park [4], Schmit [5], Vanderplaats and Weisshaar [6], Flanagan and Palazotto [7], Wurzel [8]. The study that we present here is an extension of the work given in Khalil & Ramahefarison [9] and the results are related closely with results obtained in Refs. [4,7,8]. In the following sections, the architecture of the program OPTICOM is shortly described and its more interesting capabilities are outlined. Following that, a variety of illustrative examples is offered to demonstrate the potential of this design tool in design applications of composite laminates.

2. PROGRAM ARCHITECTURE

OPTICOM is a general purpose optimization program written in Standard Fortran 77. It performs five independent functions in modular form as shown in Figure 1. A general overview of these modules has been presented in Ref. [9]. Actually OPTICOM offers numerous capabilities and features :

- optimum design for multiple load cases can be obtained. A variety of loading conditions such as mechanical forces and moments, hygrothermal forces and moments can be specified.
- three alternative optimization algorithms based on linear and non linear mathematical programming methods are available.
- three optimal objective functions (minimum weight, minimum thickness and maximum strength) can be studied. The effect of certain parameters such as the stacking sequence, ply orientation, volume fraction of fibers, failure criteria and residual stresses on these objectives can efficiently be studied also.
- optimum design of bidirectional and multidirectional long-fiber laminates as well as composites with randomly oriented short-fibers can be achieved. These laminates may or may not be balanced and/or symmetric.
- great flexibility of utilization is possible: the user can optimize a laminate that has already been defined in OPTICOM or creat by himself the desired laminate by giving the thickness, orientation and material of each ply.
- composite laminate consisting of laminae of the same material or of different materials (hybrid) can be studied.
- design variables can be ply thicknesses and/or ply orientations.
- strength constraints can be imposed with a number of failure criteria: maximum stress, maximum strain , Hill-Mises, Tsai-Wu.

Figure 1. Architecture of program OPTICOM.

Figure 2. In-plane loading and axis system.

3. APPLICATIONS

3.1. Design for minimum thickness

One of the interesting applications of OPTICOM is to determine the minimum weight and thereby the minimum thickness of an assigned laminate for a given loading condition as that shown in Figure 2. A simple procedure [10] has been developed to allow the designer to determine, accurately and rapidly, the minimum thickness with the help of simple charts. This procedure can be applied to determine the optimal thickness of any composite material laminate [9]. As an illustrative example, Figure 3 shows the minimum thickness of a $[(0/90)_2]_S$ carbon / epoxy laminate in function of the "equivalent stress", \bar{X} , which is defined by $\bar{X} = (\bar{N}_1 - \bar{N}_2) / \sqrt{2}$, ($\bar{N}_i = N_i / \sum |N_i|$; $i=1,2,6$). The effect of residual stresses on the minimum thickness will be discussed here while the effects of the stacking sequence, materials, multiple loading, ply orientation, and failure criteria on the minimum thickness were discussed in Ref. [9].

Effect of residual stresses

Residual stresses in composite laminates depend on thermoelastic properties of the material and processing temperatures. Their distribution in the various laminates is a function of stacking sequence and ply orientation. To study the effect of residual stresses on minimum thickness of a composite laminate, we have considered a $(0/90/+45/-45)_S$ AS / 3501 laminate, for example, subjected to the stress resultants $N_1 = 30$ kN/m, $N_2 = 20$ kN/m at room temperature ($T_a = 22^\circ\text{C}$) and 50% relative humidity. In this case, the stress-free temperature is the cure temperature ($T_R = 177^\circ\text{C}$) and therefore $\Delta T = T_a - T_R = -155^\circ\text{C}$, and the moisture content $\Delta H = 0.9\%$ [11].

Figure 3. Minimum thickness of carbon / epoxy cross-ply laminate.

Figure 4. Effect of residual stresses on minimum thickness.

Figure 4 shows the effect of residual stresses on the minimum thickness of the laminate. A glance at this figure shows that the absorbed humidity increases the minimum thickness by about 1.5% in contrast to the effect of the residual thermal stresses which is practically negligible. This effect is explained by the fact that the absorbed moisture produces expansional strains which counteract the thermal contraction strains produced by cooling the laminate from its elevated cure temperature [12]. In addition, the combined stress field due to the elastic, thermal and moisture induced fields is dominated by the hygrometric field alone when the moisture content is greater than the critical value (0.5 to 0.7 percent moisture content) [13].

3.2. Design for maximum strength

3.2.1. Optimal orientation

In this section, other capabilities of OPTICOM are demonstrated through the design of composite laminates for maximum strength. Here, the first ply failure (FPF) criterion is used as the objective function where the optimal laminate designed has the most strength in the sense of first ply failure [4].

The first ply failure criterion is:

$$Q = \varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_6^2 \quad (1)$$

then the optimal design problem is to minimize the value of Q . The smaller the Q value, the stronger the laminate in FPF criterion. The objective function Q depends only on the ply orientation α for a given stress loading (N_1, N_2, N_6). Therefore, the main task of the optimization process is to find the optimal orientation α^* for a given stress loading. The stress resultants N_i ($i=1,2,6$) are normalized by the largest value so that $-1 \leq N_i \leq 1$. As a result, the laminate thickness h is set to 1.

The optimal orientation α^* of various symmetric laminates are obtained under various loading conditions. As illustrative example, α^* optimum of $[0/90/\alpha/-\alpha]_s$ T300/5208 laminate is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Optimal orientation of $[0/90/\alpha/-\alpha]_s$ laminate.

Figure 6. Failure envelope of $(0/90)_2$ laminate.

3.2.2. Failure surface and minimum number of plies

The quadratic interaction failure criterion of Tsai-Wu in stress-space takes the form [11]:

$$F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j + F_i \sigma_i - 1 \leq 0 \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (2)$$

The failure envelope in normal stress resultant space- or the principal stress plane - for $(0/90)_2$ cross-ply laminate is shown in Figure 6. If simultaneous failure of all plies is an optimum condition for a laminate design, it is possible to achieve it only in the quadrants I and III where the two failure envelopes intersect. Of all possible stress ratio vectors in both quadrants, those to the intersecting points are the longest, which means an optimum condition for laminate design [8]. There is no coincidence of failure envelopes in quadrants II and IV and consequently no simultaneous failure. But as before the optimum design is characterized by the longest stress ratio vector.

On the other hand, stating the failure criterion in strain-space is often more convenient than in stress-space because failure envelopes in strain-space remain fixed for each ply orientation, independent of the stiffness. The failure criterion in strain-space can be rewritten as [11]:

$$G_{ij} \epsilon_i \epsilon_j + G_i \epsilon_i - 1 \leq 0 \quad (i,j=1,2,6) \quad (3)$$

Introducing the strength ratio:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_{\text{allowable}}}{\sigma_{\text{applied}}} = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{allowable}}}{\epsilon_{\text{applied}}} \quad (4)$$

the failure criterion can be solved for R:

$$[G_{ij} \epsilon_i \epsilon_j] R^2 + [G_i \epsilon_i] R - 1 = 0 \quad (5)$$

There are two roots, R and R', corresponding to strain vectors piercing the failure envelope in opposite directions. Once the lowest strength ratio of a given laminate configuration (thickness h) for given stress resultants is known the minimum ply number can be calculated [8].

$$n_{\text{min}} = \frac{h}{h_0 \cdot R} \quad (6)$$

where h_0 is the single ply thickness.

Particular interest is directed towards the minimum number of the angle- and cross-ply laminates. The impact of individual failure envelopes on the minimum ply requirements for angle-ply glass / epoxy laminate in the principal stress plane is depicted in Figure 7-a,b for quadrants I and IV, II and III respectively. For reasons of comparison, N_I was kept constant at ± 1 MN/m and N_{II} was changed in discrete steps [8].

Figure 7. Variation of minimum number of plies of $(\alpha/\alpha)_s$ glass/epoxy laminate with load ratio and ply orientation.

This figure shows that:

- a minimum ply number corresponding to an optimum ply angle exists for quadrants I and III none exist for quadrants II and IV. For example, α optimum is found to be 45° for stress ratios $N_I / N_{II} = \pm 1$.
- as N_{II} increases, α optimum increases also until 75° at $N_I / N_{II} = 1 / 10$. This angle becomes 85° at $N_I / N_{II} = -1 / -10$.
- at higher values of N_{II} , little deviations from the optimum orientation may strongly increase the ply number required.
- in quadrant III, generally fewer plies are required.

On the other hand, for T300 / 5208 cross-ply laminate, the required ply number in function of the cross-ply ratios is given in Figure 8-(a) for stress ratios $N_I / N_{II} = \pm 1$ and in Figure 8-(b) for $N_I / N_{II} = \pm 1/3$. This figure indicates that :

- for $N_I / N_{II} = \pm 1$, the optimum number of plies exists at 1/1 ply-ratio (i.e. for $(0/90)$ laminate) in quadrants I and III, and at 4 / 1 ply ratio (i.e. for $(0_4 / 90)$ laminate) in quadrant IV.
- For $N_I / N_{II} = \pm 1/3$, the optimum ply number in quadrant I is at $(0 / 90_3)$ laminate, in quadrant III at $(0 / 90_4)$ laminate and in quadrant IV at $(0_3 / 90_2)$ laminate.

Figure 8. Minimum number of plies of T300/5208 cross-ply laminate

3.3. Composites with randomly oriented fibers

In this section, another application of OPTICOM concerning the optimum design of composites with randomly oriented fibers will be presented. To determine the elastic constants of this composite construction, the basic assumption considered is that its behaviour is equivalent to that of a laminate having infinite number of layers oriented in as many directions as possible. Of course, this analogy is applicable only if the impregnated fibers are long enough (25-50 mm) to allow load transfer from the matrix to the fibers [14]. This equivalent laminate is necessarily balanced and symmetric about the midplane and its in-plane properties are identical in all possible directions. Accordingly, it could be considered as an isotropic laminate in the plane (1-2).

The analytical procedure is explicitly described in Ref. [14] but the general stress-strain relations are rewritten here for convenience:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_6 \end{bmatrix} = h \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & U_4 & 0 \\ U_4 & U_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U_5 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1^0 \\ \epsilon_2^0 \\ \epsilon_6^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{h^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & U_4 & 0 \\ U_4 & U_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U_5 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1^0 \\ k_2^0 \\ k_6^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Knowing the invariants U 's, which are functions of the stiffness coefficients Q_{ij} , the in-plane strains and the curvatures of the "equivalent laminate" can directly be determined. On the other hand, the elastic constants E_r , ν_r , G_r which are respectively the Young's modulus, the Poisson's ratio and the shear modulus of the randomly oriented fiber composite can be calculated by simplified relations similar to that developed by Manera for the glass / resin composites [14]. These simplified relations are functions of the volume fraction of fibers, V_f , fiber modulus, E_f , and matrix modulus, E_m . Once the elastic constants are calculated, the stiffness constants, Q_{ij} , and thereby the invariants, U 's, can immediately be determined [14].

Now, the minimum thickness and the maximum strength of randomly oriented fiber composites are calculated and plotted in graphs following the same procedure discussed in sections 3.1 and 3.2. It has been found that the minimum thickness of this composite construction changes, in function of the stress resultants, in the same manner as that of the multi-layer laminate even if its optimal value is greater. On the other hand, the maximum strength represented by Q_{min} of kevlar 49 / epoxy randomly-oriented composite is given in Figure 9. If the simplified relations are used, the effect of volume fraction of glass fibers, V_f , in a glass / epoxy composite on Q_{min} can be shown in Figure 10. This figure indicates that the higher the volume fraction of fibers, V_f , the lower will be the Q_{min} and consequently the higher will be the strength. This is a logical result as the strength and stiffness of this composite increase with the increase in V_f [10].

Figure 9. Q_{min} for max. strength of kevlar 49 / epoxy-randomly oriented fibers.

Figure 10. Effect of V_f on Q_{min} of glass / epoxy-randomly oriented fibers.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A general purpose program for the optimum design of composite laminates has been developed and thoroughly tested. This program has been designed to be compact and efficient enough to run on microcomputers (compatible IBM-PC, for example) as well as on high speed computers (HP computer, for example).

It has a modular architecture and offers great flexibility of utilization. Moreover, it requires no knowledge of computer programming or optimization techniques. Therefore, it can be used in the preliminary design to satisfy the needs of small and medium industries.

Numerous illustrative examples and charts have been presented which demonstrate the performance and efficiency of the program. The effect of certain parameters on the design objectives has been studied also.

Further developments strengthening the capabilities of the program are underway. They are :

- integration of the program with a suitable finite element code for optimization of structural systems
- optimization of an aircraft stiffened panel and of sandwich structures
- optimization of structural systems with dynamic response.

References

1. Shin, Y.S., Haftka, R.T., Watson, L.T., Plaut, R.H., *Design of Laminated Plates for Maximum Buckling Load*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 23, April 1989, pp. 348-369.
2. Vanderplaats, G.A., *Numerical Optimization Techniques for Engineering Design with Applications*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1984, pp. 26-54, 104-116, 121-140.
3. Minoux, M., *Programmation Mathématique : Théorie et Algorithmes*, Tome 1, Dunod, 1983, pp. 31-53, 95-111.
4. Park, W.J., *An Optimal Design of Simple Symmetric Laminates Under the First Ply Failure Criterion*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 16, July-1982, pp. 341-355.
5. Schmit, L.A., *The Structural Synthesis Concept and its Potential Role in the Design with Composites*, Mechanics of Composite Material, Proceedings of the Fifth Symposium on Naval Structural Mechanics, May 8-10, 1976.
6. Vanderplaats, G.A., Weisshaar, T.A., *Optimum Design of Composite Structures*, International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 27, 1989, pp. 437-448.
7. Flanagan, G., Palazotto, A.N., *Composite Laminate Optimization Program Suitable for Microcomputers*, Computers & Structures, Vol. 22, No. 6, 1986, pp. 995-1009.
8. Wurzel, D.P., *On the Design and Optimization of Bidirectional Composites*, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, Vol. 2, 1983, pp. 178-195.
9. Khalil, M., Ramahefarison, E., *OPTICOM: Un Logiciel d'Optimisation des Stratifiés Composites sur Micro-ordinateur*, Proceedings of STRUCOME 92, Paris, November 16-19, 1992, pp. 489-501.
10. Gay, D., *Matériaux Composites*, Hermes, Paris, Londres, Lausanne, 1987, pp. 48-63, 398-409.
11. Tsai, S.W., Hahn, H.T., *Introduction to Composite Materials*, Technomic Publishing Co., Inc., 1980, pp. 277-327.
12. Harper, B.D., *The Effects of Moisture Induced Swelling Upon the Shapes of Antisymmetric Cross-Ply Laminates*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 21, January 1987, pp. 36-48.
13. Mukhopadhyay, A.K., Sierakowski, R.L., *On Sandwich Beams with Laminate Facings and Honeycomb Cores Subjected to Hygrothermal Loads*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 24, April 1990, pp. 382-400.
14. Manera, M., Massot, J.J., Morel, G., Verchery, G., *Manuel de Calcul des Composites Verre/Résine*, Pluralis, Paris, 1988, pp. 147-151.